

Influence of School Environment on Emotional Maturity of High School Students

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ABSTRACT

The present study aimed to study the influence of school environment and its dimensions on emotional maturity of high school students. The investigator has used simple random sampling technique to select the sample for the present investigation. The representative sample consisted of 972 high school students. Survey method of research was adopted for the present study. The tools used in the study were Emotional Maturity Scale and School Environment Scale. The investigator used regression analysis to find out the influence of dimensions of school environment on emotional maturity of high school students. The results showed that there is significant influence of school environment and its dimensions such as creative stimulation, cognitive encouragement, permissiveness and physical school environment on emotional maturity of high school students. One of the dimension namely creative stimulation has more impact on emotional maturity of high school students.

KEYWORDS : School Environment, Emotional Maturity, Tirunelveli District, Regression Analysis

INTRODUCTION

Child spends most of the time at the school interacting with the school environment. And, it stands as one of the basic factors of learning. Bertrand Russell (1984) says, "I have no doubt in my own mind that the ideal school is better than the ideal home...because it allows more light and air, more freedom of movement, and more companionship of competencies." Thus in any socio-political system stands as a sub-system and functionally works as socializing the individuals to develop commitments and capacities which are essential pre-requisites of their future role performance expected by the society. Positive social relationships and attitudes about school are as important to the environment as are safe and well-kept buildings and grounds. A safe, clean, and well-maintained school with a positive psychosocial climate and culture can foster emotional maturity, which in turn boosts students health as well as students' educational achievement. The psychological environment includes the physical, emotional and social conditions that affect the well-being of students. Students embrace their environment when they believe that the adults in the school care about their learning and about them as individuals. Students are more likely to succeed when they feel a good bond to School. As Individuals, students who perceive their teachers and School administration as creating a caring, well-structured learning environment in which expectations are high, clear, fair are more likely to be connected to the school and thrive. In the school, the teachers have the new environment of the school the child's physical, emotional, mental, moral and social development takes a new shape. This new shape puts him much ahead in the race of development.

SCHOOL ENVIRONMENT

A healthy school environment includes the physical and aesthetic surroundings and the psychosocial climate and culture of the school. Factors that influence the physical environment include the school building and the area surrounding it, biological or chemical agents, and physical conditions such as temperature, noise and lighting. The psychological environment includes the physical, emotional and social conditions that affect the well-being of students and staff.

EMOTIONAL MATURITY

Emotional maturity is that characteristics of emotional behaviour that is generally attained by an adult after the expiry of his adolescence period. After attained emotional maturity, he is able to demonstrate a well balanced emotional behavior in his day-to-day life. A person may be set to be emotionally matured if he has in his positions almost all types of emotional – positive or negative and is able to express from at the appropriate time on appropriate degree. The characteristics of an emotionally matured person. (Mangal, 2007) "Mature" emotional

behavior at any level of growth is that which most fully reflects the fruits of healthy development in all the interaction aspects of the growing persons make up. (Charles E Skinner, 2004). According to Singh and Bhargava, (1990) Emotional maturity is not only the effective determinant of personality pattern but also helps to control the growth of an adolescent's development. A person who is able to keep his emotions under control who is able to brook delay and to suffer without self-pity might still be emotionally stunned.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The environment is more than physical space because it contains the emotions of the children who spend time in it, the staff that work there and the parents who leave their children there. The emotional environment is an invisible measure of 'feelings' – sometimes it can have a 'feel-good' factor where the children, staff and parents feel positive, and at others it can have a 'not-so-good' feel about it when children, staff or parent are down or unhappy. Maintaining positive feelings is important for staff, children and parents, but equally. If they feel safe in the emotional environment, children can express their feelings safely, knowing that their parents or staff are nearby to help them if they feel overwhelmed by these. Teaching children ways to talk about and express their feelings allows them to externalise them safely, rather than to cover them up and leave them hidden away. Feelings which are expressed in safety are far easier to deal with than those which are left unresolved. So school environment plays a main role in the development of emotional maturity of high school students. With this background, the investigator wants to study the influence of school environment and its dimensions on emotional maturity of high school students.

METHOD OF RESEARCH

Survey method of research was adopted for the present study.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

To study the influence of school environment and its dimensions on emotional maturity of high school students.

HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY

There is no significant influence of school environment and its dimensions on emotional maturity of high school students.

TOOLS USED

Emotional Maturity Scale was developed and validated by the investigator to measure the emotional maturity of the high school students. In this Scale, at the end of each statement five graded options were given namely – 'Strongly Agree', 'Agree', 'Undecided', 'Disagree' and 'Strongly Disagree' having scores 5,4,3,2 and 1 for positive statements

and reverse for negative statements. School Environment Scale was developed and validated by the investigator to measure the school environment of the high school students. In School Environment this Scale, at the end of each statement five graded options were given namely – ‘Always’, ‘Agree’, ‘Sometimes’, ‘Very Rarely’ and ‘Never’ having scores 5,4,3,2 and 1 for positive statements and reverse for negative statements. The scale consisted of five dimensions i.e., creative stimulation, cognitive encouragement, permissiveness, acceptance and physical school environment.

POPULATION

The high school students studying in all schools in Tirunelveli district of Tamilnadu state are constituted as population for the study. But it was not humanly possible to include all of them in the study. Keeping in mind time, physical and financial constraints, it was decided to select a small proportion of them for sake of conducting this research study.

Table – 1
Influence of school environment and its dimensions on emotional maturity of High School Students

Predictors	B	SE	β	t	Sig.	R	R ²	F	Sig.
Constant	131.800	4.667		28.23	0.00*	0.325	0.322	93.15	0.00*
Creative Stimulation	0.573	0.081	0.279	7.044	0.00*				
Cognitive Encouragement	0.456	0.103	0.187	4.423	0.00*				
Permissiveness	0.282	0.104	0.104	2.715	0.007*				
Acceptance	-0.013	0.101	-0.004	-0.130	0.897*				
Physical School Environment	0.153	.037	0.123	4.122	0.000*				

*Significant at 1% level

The result of the multiple regression (R) shows that there is significant correlation between the dependent variable – emotional maturity and the dimensions of school environment. Positive B values indicate significant relationship between emotional maturity and dimensions of school environment except acceptance. Except acceptance, all the predictors have significant t-values, those dimensions have a strong influence on emotional maturity. The β value for creative stimulation is greater than the other predictors, which implies that its impact is more. The high F-value indicates significant relationship between predictors and dependent variable. Results indicate that 32% of emotional maturity in high school students depends on the dimensions of school environment and the remaining 68% is due to variables other than the dimensions of school environment.

FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

There is significant influence of school environment and its dimensions such as creative stimulation, cognitive encouragement, permissiveness and physical school environment on emotional maturity of high school students. One of the dimension namely creative stimulation has more impact on emotional maturity of high school students.

EDUCATIONAL IMPLICATION OF THE STUDY

The impact of creative stimulation on emotional maturity of high school students is more in this study. Creative Stimulation refers to “teacher’s activities to provide conditions and opportunities to stimulate creative thinking.” Creative or innovative thinking is the kind of thinking that leads to new insights, novel approach-

SAMPLE

The sample of the study comprised high school students of Tirunelveli district of Tamilnadu state. The investigator has used simple random sampling technique to select the sample for the present investigation. The representative sample consists of 972 high school students from 38 schools, randomly in 19 blocks of Tirunelveli district in Tamilnadu.

STATISTICAL TECHNIQUE USED

The investigator used regression analysis to find out the influence of school and its dimensions of environment on emotional maturity of high school students.

ANALYSIS OF DATA

H0 There is no significant influence of school environment and its dimensions on emotional maturity of high school students.

es, fresh perspectives, whole new ways of understanding and conceiving of things. Imagination enhances our ability of expression which evolves more philosophical thought patterns. Also, imagination of something for a long time brings an emotional attachment to it. This drives the need to bring them to reality - either to realize one’s dreams, or to share it with others, etc. - in essence catalysing the natural evolution of perception. The most important informal function of school is to develop the child emotionally. For this, the entire environment of school must be artistic. In other words, there should be garden, flower plants and other beautiful natural objects. The school building and the campus should be neat and clean. The walls of the room should be white washed annually and rooms be decorated tastefully. Trips, tours, exhibitions and debates also stimulate the emotional and aesthetic sense of children who can further be infused with a sense of admiration towards truth, beauty and goodness, the high ideals of human life.

CONCLUSION

Education can play an important role in balanced emotional development of the child. In fact school is the place after home which influence the emotional behavior of the child most. The healthy development of the child’s emotions can take place only when the school environment and extracurricular activities are according to his emotions. The teacher can present good examples create desire to follow good ideals, contact suitable environment in order to develop desirable emotions and can prevent undesirable emotions from growing.

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